

Productivity of concepts in Serbian Wordnet

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Abstract

Wordnet is an online lexical database designed for use under program control. It is based on word meaning, rather than word forms. All of the words that can express a given sense are grouped together in a synonym set (synset) representing a concept. All concepts are linked with semantic relations forming semantic network. The network is basically a forest consisting of concept hierarchies rooted in top ontology concepts. In this paper we describe several measures for determining productivity of some concept in order to find those concepts that most effectively represent hierarchy they belong to. They are different from top ontology concepts (which are too general), and could be considered as ontological concepts associated with classes characterized by hierarchies rooted in them. Determining most productive concepts may be applied to text classification in different ways. Information retrieval and information extraction could be made more efficient if they are based on such kind of classification.

1. Introduction

The main goal of the Princeton Wordnet (PWN) (Miller, 1995), or simply Wordnet, developed by George Miller and his associates was to serve as a mental lexicon in the scope of psycholinguistic research projects. In a traditional dictionary, lexical items are listed alphabetically, giving definitions for each sense. Wordnet, in contrast, is based on word meaning; all of the words that can express a given sense are grouped together in a synonym set, or synset representing a concept. It is a set of approximately 100.000 concepts interconnected by semantic relations to form a semantic network. A new dimension to the Wordnet project was added by EuroWordnet (EWN) (Vossen 1998), a multilingual database with wordnets for Dutch, Italian, Spanish, German, French, Czech and Estonian. The aim of BalkaNet, the Balkan wordnet project (BWN) (Stamou et al., 2002), was to develop aligned semantic networks for several Balkan languages, namely Bulgarian, Greek, Romanian, Serbian and Turkish, as well as to extend the existing network for Czech, initially developed within the EWN project. The BWN and EWN wordnets are all linked to an Inter-Lingual-Index (ILI), which makes it possible to relate similar concepts in different languages, a feature that can be used, among others, for cross-language information retrieval. The BWN, as a multilingual database, in its initial phase followed the basic pattern set by EWN. The formation of databases started from a translation of a common set of concepts named "basic concepts" (see paragraph below) in EWN. Further development of the BWN databases was aimed at maintaining a common set of concepts to be shared among languages, while at the same time, giving liberty to each Wordnet to introduce specific concepts for its own language on an as needed basis. In the absence of both an explanatory dictionary for Serbian and an English/Serbian dictionary in electronic form, translation of English synsets from PWN into Serbian was done manually. It brought up the question of validation of Serbian synsets on corpora. The use of monolingual and multilingual corpora for synset validation led to introduction of new literals or removal of existing ones from a synset (Krstev et al., 2003; Obradović et al., 2003).

Wordnet is an on-line lexical reference system whose design is inspired by current psycholinguistic theories of human lexical memory. When psychologists think about the organization of lexical memory it is nearly always the organization of nouns that they have in mind. Nominal concepts are organized hierarchically into levels, from specific to generic. The top-most, or most generic level of the hierarchy is almost vacuous semantically. If these hierarchies were inheritance systems, they seldom go more than ten levels deep, and those cases usually contain technical levels that are not part of the everyday vocabulary. These hierarchies of nominal concepts have been said to have a level, somewhere in the middle, where most of the distinguishing features are attached. It is referred to as the base level of the noun lexicon, and concepts at this level are "basic concepts". These concepts are not too specific and not too general. For lexical concepts at the base level, people can list many distinguishing features. Above the base level, descriptions are brief and general. Below the base level, little is added to features that distinguish "basic concepts".

In order to formalize the notion of "basic concept", we introduce the notion of "productivity" of concept that represents how much that concept effectively represents hierarchy which belongs to. In this manner, "basic concepts" could be defined as all the concepts that have value of productivity in some range near the largest value of the defined measure of "productivity". These "basic concepts" could be considered like the most representative concepts of the hierarchy which belong to.

Measures of productivity could be defined in many different ways. For example, for some selected concept, it could be defined as a product of the number of all descendants (or just all leaves) of that concept and the distance of that concept from the root of the hierarchy (number of concepts that are in its path to the root). Measure of productivity of a concept could also be defined as a ratio of the number of its in the tree rooted in that concept, to the number of descendants in trees rooted in his siblings (concepts at the same level as the considered concept). The choice between those measures depends on the purpose of productivity measurement.

Wordnet has been used in numerous natural language processing tasks. It is widely used in text classification which is an important application of machine learning.

Most productive concepts and hierarchies rooted in them may support a new approach to text classification.

The paper proceeds as follows. In section 2 we present the structure of Serbian wordnet. Section 3 presents different measures of concept productivity. In section 4 we present comparison of Serbian and English Wordnet. In section 5 one example of most productive concepts is presented for hierarchy rooted in “entity”. Finally, section 6 presents some examples of applying most productive concepts to natural language processing and section 7 presents the conclusion and future work.

2. Serbian wordnet - SWN

Serbian wordnet (SWN) is a lexical-semantic network of Serbian language (Pavlović-Lažetić, 2006). The structure of SWN is basically the same as the structure of American wordnet for English, PWN. It is based on concepts called synsets. Only words of the same Part of Speech (PoS) (e.g. **nouns, verbs**) can belong to the same synset. A synset ID is assigned to every word. Words in the same synset have the same synset ID. Since one word can have several meanings, it can belong to more than one synset. Each literal string is accompanied by a unique sense number denoting **its meaning within a particular synset**.

SWN contains only nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs. It presently contains approximately 14000 sets of synonyms (Krstev et al, 2008). Except for the synonymy relation, defining the concept of a synset, the most important relations between concepts is the hypernym / hyponym (is-a) relation. Because there is usually only one hypernym, this semantic relation organizes the meanings of nouns into a hierarchical structure. The synsets for nouns referring to actions are much more structured than synsets for verbs (more exactly, there is a long and unstructured list of top-level synsets for verb meanings). So, we took into consideration just noun concepts. There are 9 top-level synsets in Serbian Wordnet for noun meanings that correspond to relatively distinct semantic fields: “entity” (“entitet” in Serbian), “abstraction” (“apstrakcija”), “group” (“grupa”), “act” (“akt”), “psychological feature” (“psihičko svojstvo”), “state” (“stanje”), “event” (“dogadjaj”), “phenomenon” (“fenomen”) and “possession” (“svojina”).

All national wordnets share the same data structure in XML. An example of a synset from the SWN and PWN, corresponding to the concept “deity” (“božanstvo”) is represented in Figure 1\.

The meaning of (some of) the elements in this figure is the following: ID is the synset identifier, unique across different languages, POS is the part of speech, ILR is the ID of a concept (synset) related to this one by a relation of the type TYPE, etc.

Table 1 represents the number of synsets in SWN per specific PoS, PoS related distribution of synsets in SWN, number of synsets and PoS related distribution of synsets in PWN, and last column in the table represents ratio between number of synsets in SWN and PWN per specific PoS.

<pre> <SYNSET> <ID> ENG20-08904620-n </ID> <SYNONYM> <LITERAL>božanstvo<SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL> </SYNONYM> <DEF> Natprirodno biće koje se obožava zbog verovanja da upravlja nekim delom sveta ili nekim aspektima zivota ili zato što personifikuje silu. </DEF> <POS>n</POS> <ILR>ENG20-08903509-n<TYPE>hypernym</TYPE></ILR> <ILR>ENG20-07660421-n<TYPE>holo_member</TYPE></ILR> </SYNSET> </pre>
<pre> <SYNSET> <ID> ENG20-08904620-n </ID> <SYNONYM> <LITERAL>deity <SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL> <LITERAL>divinity <SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL> <LITERAL>god <SENSE>2</SENSE></LITERAL> <LITERAL>immortal <SENSE>2</SENSE></LITERAL> </SYNONYM> <DEF> any supernatural being worshipped as controlling some part of the world or some aspect of life or who is the personification of a force. </DEF> <POS>n</POS> <ILR>ENG20-08903509-n<TYPE>hypernym</TYPE></ILR> <ILR>ENG20-07660421-n<TYPE>holo_member</TYPE></ILR> <ILR>ENG20-00670299-v <TYPE>eng_derivative</TYPE></ILR> </SYNSET> </pre>

Figure 1. A synset of the Serbian and its corresponding synset of the English Wordnet

PoS	SWN	percents (SWN)	PWN	percents (PWN)	PWN/SWN
nouns	11 155	80.1%	79 689	69%	7.1
verbs	1 945	14%	13 508	12%	6.9
adjectives	793	5.7%	18 563	16%	23.4
adverbs	27	0.2%	3 664	3%	135.7
total	13 920	100%	115 424	100%	8.3

Table 1: PoS related distribution of synsets in SWN and PWN

3. Measures of concept productivity

As we mentioned earlier, we took into consideration just noun concepts and hypernym / hyponym relations between them.

In order to formalize the notion of "basic concept", we have introduced the notion of "productivity" of concepts. In this manner, the “basic concepts” could be defined as all concepts that have value of productivity in some range close to the largest value of defined measure of productivity. These “basic concepts” could be considered

as the most representative concepts of the hierarchies which belong to.

Measures of concept productivity could be defined in different ways. For example, for a selected concept, it could be defined as a product of the number of all descendants (or just leaves) of that concept and distance of that concept from the root of the corresponding hierarchy (number of concepts that are in its path to the root). Formally, for a selected concept c which belongs to a hierarchy rooted in the concept $root$, it could be represented as follows:

Measure 1:

$$ProductivityOfConcept(c) = ND(c)^{\alpha} * d(c)^{\beta}$$

Measure 2:

$$ProductivityOfConcept(c) = NL(c)^{\alpha} * d(c)^{\beta}$$

where $ND(c)$ is the number of descendants in a tree rooted in the selected concept c , $NL(c)$ is the number of leaves in the tree rooted in c , and d is a distance of c from the root of the hierarchy. α and β are parameters which determine weights (or significance) that the number of descendants (or leaves), and the distance from the root, respectively, have in the overall measure. In our experiments we have used *Measure 1* with $\alpha=1$ and $\beta=2$. If α has bigger and β has lower value, then concept with the largest value of this measure will go upper to the hierarchy which belongs to.

At the other hand, measure of productivity of a concept could be defined as a ratio of the number of descendants in a tree rooted in the selected concept, to the number of descendants in trees rooted in his siblings. Formally, it could be represented as follows:

Measure 3:

$$ProductivityOfConcept(c) = ND(c) / \text{summ}(ND(\text{siblings}))$$

where $ND(c)$ is the number of descendants in the tree rooted in the concept c .

It is possible to define measure of productivity at many other deferent ways. The choice between these measures depends on the purpose of productivity measurement.

"possession" "svojina"	most productive concept (SWN)	percents, level (SWN)	most productive concept (PWN)	percents, level (PWN)
Measure 1	"cost" "potrošnja"	10%, 6	"cost" "potrošnja"	30%, 6
Measure 2	"cost" "potrošnja"	10%, 6	"cost" "potrošnja"	30%, 6
Measure 3	"estate" "imanje"	6.25%, 4	"financial loss" "finansijski gubitak"	33%, 4

Table 2: Most productive concepts for the hierarchy rooted at "possession" in SWN and PWN using deferent measures

For example, the most productive concept for hierarchy rooted at "entity" ("entitet") (which has the largest number of concepts), if we use *Measure 1* with $\alpha=1$ and $\beta=2$, is the concept "organism" or

"being". Tree rooted in that concept contains 44% of all concepts in that hierarchy in English wordnet (PWN) and 55% in SWN and it is at the third level of hierarchy (see section 5). For the hierarchy rooted at "possession" ("svojina") (which has the least number of concepts), if we use the same measure, most productive concept is "cost" ("potrošnja"). Tree rooted in that concept contains 10% of all concepts in that hierarchy in SWN and 30% in PWN and it is at the sixth level of hierarchy. Table 2 represents the most productive concepts for the concept "possession" ("svojina") using all three previously defined measures.

4. Comparison of Serbian and English wordnets

Since a semantic relation is a relation between meanings, and since meanings can be represented by synsets, it is natural to think of semantic relations as pointers between synsets. The database is restricted to the relations suggested by the psycholinguistic data: synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, hypernymy, and three types of meronymy and holonymy. These and other similar relations serve to organize the mental lexicon. They can all be thought of, or represented by, pointers or labeled arcs from one synset to another.

The relations between synsets in SWN and PWN are summarized in Table 3. These relations in SWN have automatically been inherited from the PWN, but then they were all manually checked.

relation	PoS/PoS (N=Nouns, V=Verbs, A=Adjectives)	SWN	PWN	PWN /SWN
hypernym	N/N V/V	13034	94844	7.28
near antonym	N/N A/A V/V	680	7642	11.2
holo part	N/N	701	8636	12.3
verb group	V/V	163	1748	10.72
holo member	N/N	3309	12205	3.69
be in state	A/N	268	1296	4.84
subevent	V/V	76	409	5.38
causes	V/V	58	439	7.57
derived	A/N	326	6809	20.89
particle	A/V	10	401	40.1

Table 3: Distribution of relations between synsets in SWN and PWN

Wordnet includes the following semantic relations:

- *Synonymy* is Wordnet's basic relation, because Wordnet uses sets of synonyms (*synsets*) to represent word senses. It can be used to map words with similar meanings together e.g. "happy" and "glad".
- *Hyponymy* (subordination) and its inverse, *hypernymy* (superordination) can be used to generalize noun and verb meanings to a higher level of abstraction¹. The hyponym inherits all the features of the more generic concept and adds at least one feature that distinguishes it from its

¹ The hypernymy relation is defined only for nouns and verbs.

superordinate and from other hyponyms of that superordinate. The Figure 2 shows an idealized model of a part of the Wordnet semantic hierarchy and Figure 3 shows it as a part of an XML document.

- *Antonymy* (opposing-name) is especially important in organizing the meanings of adjectives. The antonym of a word x is sometimes not-x, but not always. For example, “rich” and “poor” are antonyms, but to say that someone is not rich does not mean that he must be poor.
- *Meronymy* (part-name) and its inverse, *holonymy* (whole-name), are complex semantic relations. Wordnet distinguishes *component* parts, *substantive* parts, and *member* parts. For example, “paper” is a meronym of “book”, since paper is a part of a book.
- *Troponymy* (manner-name) is for verbs what hyponymy is for nouns. The "kind-of" relation among nouns corresponds to a "manner-of" relation among the verbs. For example, “walk” is a troponym of “move” and “limp” is a troponym of “walk”.
- *Entailment* refers to a relationship between two verbs. A verb x entails y if the truth of y follows logically from the truth of x. The relation of entailment is unilateral, i.e., it is one way relation. For example, concept "kill" entails concept "die".

Figure 2. A piece of the Wordnet semantic hierarchy (idealized model)

In the previous section we have defined several measures for a concept that may determine its “productivity” or how much that concept effectively represents hierarchy which belongs to. “Basic concepts” could be considered as the most productive concepts for the corresponding hierarchy.

```

<SYNSET>
<ID> ENG20-04387884-n </ID>
<SYNONYM>
  <LITERAL>weapon</SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL>
  <LITERAL>arm</SENSE>2</SENSE></LITERAL>
  <LITERAL>weapon system</SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL>
</SYNONYM>
<DEF>
any instrument or instrumentality used in fighting or hunting
</DEF>
<USAGE>he was licensed to carry a weapon</USAGE>
<POS>n</POS>
<ILR>ENG20-03443087-n</TYPE>hypernym</TYPE></ILR>
</SYNSET>

<SYNSET>
<ID> ENG20-03489316-n </ID>
<SYNONYM>
  <LITERAL>knife </SENSE>2</SENSE></LITERAL>
</SYNONYM>
<DEF>a weapon with a handle and blade with a sharp point</DEF>
<DOMAIN>military</DOMAIN>
<POS>n</POS>
<ILR>ENG20-04387884-n </TYPE>hypernym</TYPE></ILR>
</SYNSET>

<SYNSET>
<ID> ENG20-03340812-n </ID>
<SYNONYM>
  <LITERAL>gun</SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL>
</SYNONYM>
<DEF> a weapon that discharges a missile at high velocity (especially
from a metal tube or barrel)</DEF>
<DOMAIN>military</DOMAIN>
<POS>n</POS>
<ILR>ENG20-04387884-n </TYPE>hypernym</TYPE></ILR>
</SYNSET>

<SYNSET>
<ID> ENG20-03222124-n </ID>
<SYNONYM>
  <LITERAL> firearm </SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL>
  <LITERAL> piece </SENSE>7</SENSE></LITERAL>
  <LITERAL> small-arm </SENSE>1</SENSE></LITERAL>
</SYNONYM>
<DEF> a portable gun </DEF>
<USAGE> he wore his firearm in a shoulder holster </USAGE>
<DOMAIN>military</DOMAIN>
<POS>n</POS>
<ILR> ENG20-03340812-n </TYPE>hypernym</TYPE></ILR>
</SYNSET>
  
```

Figure 3. A piece of the Wordnet semantic hierarchy (XML representation)

In Table 4 results are given for most productive concepts (MPC) in SWN and PWN for all hierarchies rooted in 9 top-level synsets for noun meanings. Also, number of concepts in the tree rooted in the most productive concept is given in brackets, along with the percentage of those concepts with respect to all the

concepts in the corresponding hierarchy. Results in this table represent most productive concepts using *Measure 1* defined in the previous section, with parameters $\alpha=1$ and $\beta=2$.

roots	MPC(PWN)	MPC(SWN)
“entity” (“entitet”)	“organism” (“organizam”) (18997 – 44%)	“organism” (“organizam”) (2884 – 55%)
“abstraction” (“apstrakcija”)	“communication” (“komunikacija”) (4638 – 42%)	“natural language” (“prirodni jezik”) (610 – 34%)
“group” (“grupa”)	“genus” (“rod”) (3652 – 44%)	“taxon” (“takson”) (1826 – 81%)
“human action” (“ljudska aktivnost”)	“activity” (“aktivnost”) (3164 – 47%)	“activity” (“aktivnost”) (405 – 55%)
“psychological feature” (“psihičko svojstvo”)	“content” (“saznajni sadržaj”) (2214 – 46%)	“biology” (“biologija”) (31 – 8%)
“state” (“stanje”)	“disease” (“oboljenje”) (514 – 16%)	“condition” (“postojanje”) (99 – 40%)
“event” (“događaj”)	“happening” (“dešavanje”) (941 – 44%)	“group action” (“grupna akcija”) (115 – 50%)
“phenomenon” (“fenomen”)	“physical phenomenon” (“fizička pojava”) (513 – 32%)	“light” (“svetlost”) (5 – 5%)
“possession” (“svojina”)	“cost” (“potrošnja”) (233 – 31%)	“cost” (“potrošnja”) (8 – 10%)

Table 4: Most productive concepts (MPC) in noun hierarchies, using *Measure 1* of productivity with $\alpha=1$ and $\beta=2$ in SWN and PWN

From this table some differences in most productive concepts in SWN and PWN could be seen. For example, most productive concept for hierarchy rooted in “psychological feature” (“psihičko svojstvo”) in PWN is “content” (“saznajni sadržaj”) and in SWN is “biology” (“biologija”). Reason for this is that more concepts were added in SWN that are ancestors of “biology” than of some other concepts, in comparison with PWN. These differences indicate deficiency of SWN and they are good pointers to direction in which SWN should be recharged.

5. One example of the most productive concepts

In this section we present an example of determining the most productive concept for hierarchy rooted in the concept “entity” (“entitet”). In this example we have used *Measure 1* with parameters $\alpha=1$ and $\beta=2$.

As we could see in Figure 4, the most productive concept for the “entity” (“entitet”) hierarchy is “organism” (“organizam”). It contains 44% of all concepts in the corresponding hierarchy in PWN and 55% in SWN and it could be considered as the most productive concept for

that hierarchy. This concept belongs to the third level in the whole hierarchy.

<p>entity (pwn 43255 – 100%)(swn 5278 – 100%) => object, physical object (pwn 31306 – 72%) (swn 4210 – 80%) => whole, whole thing, unit (pwn 10346 – 24%)(swn 1085 – 21%) => artifact, artefact (pwn 10342 – 24%)(swn 1083 – 21%) => instrumentality, instrumentation (pwn 5291 – 12%)(swn 464 – 9%) => device (pwn 2617 – 6%)(swn 206 – 4%) => living thing, animate thing (pwn 19129 – 44%) (swn 2957 – 56%) => organism, being (pwn 18997 – 44%) (swn 2884 – 55%) => person, individual, someone, somebody, mortal, human, soul (pwn 9894 – 23%) (swn 1074 – 20%) => plant, flora, plant life (pwn 4781 – 11%) (swn 952 – 18%) => animal, animate being, beast, creature, fauna (pwn 3989 – 9%) (swn 669 – 13%)</p>
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Figure 4. Most productive concept for hierarchy rooted in the concept entity (“entitet”)

6. Applications of the most productive concepts

Because meaningful sentences are composed of meaningful words, any system that tends to process natural languages as people do must have information about words and their meanings. This information is traditionally provided through dictionaries, and machine-readable dictionaries are now widely available. But dictionary entries evolved for the convenience of human readers, not for machines. Wordnet provides a more effective combination of traditional lexicographic information and modern computing. It is designed for use under program control.

Wordnet has been used in numerous natural language processing tasks, such as part of speech tagging, word sense disambiguation, text classification, information extraction, information retrieval and so on, with considerable success.

Text classification is an important application of machine learning that can be used in a variety of contexts, including e-mail and news filtering, personal information agents and assistants, information retrieval, and automatic indexing. Text classification is the task of assigning a text document to one or more categories, based on its contents. Usually, text documents were represented as the set of words that occurred in the document, an approach that is often referred to as the *bag of words* model. A number of authors have experimented with automatic text classification systems.

Text classification could be done in different ways by applying measures of productivity. For example, some

well chosen most productive concepts could be associated with some predefined classes in the process of text classification. Text document then could be classified by considering frequency of literals (or some specific literals, e.g., named entities) in hierarchies of those most productive concepts. Information Retrieval (IR) and Information Extraction (IE) could be made more efficient if they are based on that kind of classification.

Information retrieval is concerned with locating documents relevant to user's information needs from a collection of documents. The user describes his/her information needs with a query which consists of a number of words. The information retrieval system compares the query with documents in the collection and returns the documents that are likely to satisfy the user's information requirements. It could be very useful to extend those queries by adding all literals from hierarchy of some well chosen productive concepts.

7. Conclusions and future work

In this paper we described several measures for determining productivity of a Wordnet concept in order to find those concepts that most effectively represent hierarchies which they belong to. For example, experimental results for concept "entity" show that concept "organism" could be considered as the most representative concept for the whole hierarchy rooted in "entity". That is the concept that has maximum value of defined measure of productivity. If we took into consideration all concepts that have value of productivity near maximum value, we could get more concepts that represent this hierarchy, and we could consider them as "basic concepts".

Abundant future work stems from this preliminary study. The first task is to complete this analyzing process. Instead of one most productive concept, we could take into consideration all concepts that belong to some given range of productivity. Recent experiments have suggested that text classification process in that case could be made more efficient. We plan to compare this classification scheme with existing classifying systems such as EAGLES (Sinclair 1996), to elaborate criteria for classifying documents based on most productive concepts and to experiment with this kind of text classification on a real corpus. We also plan to define adequate database structure. Another area for consideration is the IR and IE. Our experience indicates that in some cases, better results can be obtained if IR and IE are based on this kind of classification.

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